

Therapeutic Potential of Methanolic Chicory Leaves Extract Against H₂O₂-Induced Hepatotoxicity in Rats

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Abstract

Liver diseases have become a major global health challenge and may be triggered by several toxic chemicals, which include chemotherapeutic agents, thioacetamide, H₂O₂, certain antibiotics, excessive alcohol consumption, and pathogenic microbes. Hence, safeguarding a healthy liver is vital for good health and well-being. Chicory (*Cichorium intybus*) belongs to Asteraceae Family and is considered very important medicinal plant in this direction. The present study deals evaluation methanolic extracts of Chicory plant for a period of 45 days at the following dose levels; 50 and 75 mg/kg body weight/day, orally respectively. The activities were studied by assaying aspartate transaminase (AST), alanine transaminase (ALT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), total and direct bilirubin (TB) and (DB), total protein (TP), albumin (Alb), catalase (CAT) and Superoxide dismutases (SOD). The methanolic extract of *Cichorium intybus* at dose 75 mg/kg body weight/day has the highest effectiveness against H₂O₂- induced hepatotoxicity.

Keywords: *Cichorium intybus*, methanolic extract, Antioxidant activity, Hepatocytotoxicity

Introduction

Recently, especially after the appearance of various diseases and the disadvantages of the authentic drugs, human had looked back to the folk medicine, which depends mainly on the medicinal plants. Most of the world scientists tried to make the natural plant products to be replaced the synthetic drugs. (Devappa *et al.*, 2011). Common chicory, (*Cichorium intybus*) is a perennial herbaceous plant of the dandelion family Asteraceae, usually with bright blue flowers,

rarely white or pink. This is also known as blue daisy, blue dandelion, blue sailors, blue weed, bunk, coffee weed, cornflower, Hendibeh, horseweed, ragged sailors, succory, wild bachelor's buttons, and wild endive which is native in Europe, and is now common in North America, China, and Australia, where it has become widely naturalized. (Thorat and Raut, 2018). The liver is a vital organ that plays a central role in transforming and clearing chemicals and is susceptible to the toxicity from these agents.

Therefore, it is an important target organ of detoxifying drugs, xenobiotics, and oxidative stress. Hepatotoxicity is presently the most widespread pathology worldwide, representing up to 83% of all cases and the most serious health problems. Free radicals and reactive oxygen species are increasingly believed to play a crucial role in the initiation and progression of liver diseases, independent of the original causal agent (El-Sayed *et al.*, 2015). Liver function is generally impaired by xenobiotics or infections. Chronic or excessive exposure of xenobiotics leads to cirrhosis or malignant lesions in untreated cases. At present, millions of people suffer from hepatic damage induced by alcohol, chemicals and infections. Thus, acute and chronic liver diseases continue to be serious health problems in the world, (Cemek, 2010). Chemicals like paracetamol (Larson, *et al.*, 2005), carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄) (Domenicali, 2009), nitrosamines, and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons damage the liver significantly. There is a need to develop newer drugs or safer options from current available compounds which provide hepatoprotection. (Lee, *et al.*, 2007). Oxidative stress has been considered as a conjoint pathological mechanism, and it contributes to initiation and progression of

liver injury with several metabolic pathway's disorders and a depletion of endogenous antioxidant defense mechanisms. (Marra, *et al.*, 2011). Formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) is an unavoidable consequence in aerobic organisms during respiration. It has been shown that overproduction of unstable ROS leads to unwanted reactions with other groups or substances in the body, resulting in cell or tissue injury. In addition, numerous studies have revealed that uncontrolled lipid peroxidation is involved in the occurrence of many diseases, including Parkinson's, arthritis, myocardial infarction, Alzheimer's, cancer, cardiovascular disease, and liver damage. (Blomhoff, 2005; Qian, *et al.*, 2008). Chicory is well known in the folk and modern medicine for its anticancer (Lee, *et al.*, 2000), antioxidant (Mehmood *al.*, 2012), antidiabetic (Pushparaj, *et al.* 2007), anti-inflammatory (Ripoll, *et al.*, *et al.* 2007), antimicrobial (Das, *et al.*, 2016), anthelmintic (Miller, *et al.*, 2011), analgesic (Wesołowska, *et al.*, 2006), cardiovascular (Ahmed, 2009), gastroprotective (Gürbüz, *et al.*, 2002), hepatoprotective (Gilani and Janbaz, 1994), immunological (Kim, *et al.*, 2002), reproductive effects (Behnam-Rassouli, *et al.*, 2010), wound healing abilities (Süntar, *et al.*, 2012), and many

other pharmacological applications (**Das, et al., 2016** ; **Al-Snafi, 2016**). It is also important to mention the numerous active substances of this species: alkaloids, coumarins, caffeic acid derivatives, sesquiterpene lactones, flavonoids, terpenoids, and volatile compounds (**Al-Snafi, 2016**). Chicory was reported to have hepatoprotective effect against galactosamine and thioacetamide-induced hepatotoxicity (**Gadgoli and Mishra, 1997**). This hepatoprotective activity has been correlated to its ability to inhibit the free radical-mediated damage (**Jamshidzadeh et al., 2010; Driss et al., 2016**). Chicory was quite effective in detoxification and prevention of various fungal hepatic toxicities (**Kishore, et al., 2009**). In addition, it has been shown that esculetin, a phenolic compound, and cichotyboside, a sesquiterpene glycoside from the seeds of *cichorium intybus* prevented liver damage induced by paracetamol and CCl₄ (**Gilani et al., 1998**). In this paper, chicory was subjected as hepatoprotective agent against H₂O₂ induced rats.

Materials and methods

Plant collection and identification: chicory was collected from Faculty of Agriculture, Damietta University, Egypt in February

2017. The leaves were allowed to dry in a shady and well-aired place, then dried at 50 °C and grounded into a powder using commercial blender.

Extraction with Methanol (methanolic extract): 500gm dried powder of chicory leaves was macerated in 1.5 L of methanol 70 % (3 times) for 24 h at room temperature. The methanol extract was filtered through Whatman (No.1) filter paper. The filtrates were combined and evaporated using rotary evaporator under vacuum. The obtained extract was kept at 4°C till further use. (**Rampadarath et al., 2014**).

Determination of phenolics and flavonoids (HPLC): Flavonoids and polyphenolics were Quantitative by HPLC modified method of **Zuo, et al., (2002)**

Experimental animals: Adult male albino rats (150 ± 10 g) were obtained from the Memorial Institute of Ophthalmology in Giza Egypt. All the animals were kept in plastic cages and placed in a well-ventilated rat house (temperature was 22 ± 2 °C. The lighting conditions were natural light from large windows during the day and complete darkness during the night). Rats were acclimatized to laboratory conditions for 2 weeks prior to start the experiment and

were kept on a balanced diet throughout the experimental period.

Experimental design: Randomized groups of rats were divided into four groups; each group consist of 10 male rats.

Group-1: Rats kept without any treatments as control fed on standard diet, named normal control or (negative control).

Group-2: Rats were treated with 0.5 % H₂O₂ in drinking water, named diseased group or (positive control).

Group-3: Rats were treated with 0.5 % H₂O₂ in drinking water only for 15 days, then methanolic extract of chicory at orally dose of 50 mg/kg bw (chicory 50).

Group-4: Rats were treated with 0.5 % H₂O₂ in drinking water for 15 days, then methanolic extract of chicory at orally dose of 75 mg/kg bw (chicory 75).

- Plant extract was given daily by stomach tube and the blood samples were taken at 0, 15, 30 and 45 days of the experimental period for biochemical analysis.

Preparation of blood samples: Blood samples were collected from orbital sinus veins using heparinized capillary tubes at different periods (0, 15, 30, 45) into clean, dry, and labeled Eppendorf tubes (1.5 ml). The tubes contained heparin as anticoagulant (7.5 I. U/ml blood) according to (Schalm, 1986).

Determination of aspartate transaminase AST activity: The activity of aspartate aminotransferase was determined by enzymatic colorimetric method in plasma as described by Young, (1990).

Determination of alanine transaminase ALT activity: The activity of alanine aminotransferase was evaluated by enzymatic colorimetric method in plasma according to the method by Young, (1990).

Determination of alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity: Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) was determined calorimetrically in plasma as described by Moss, *et al*, (1987).

Determination of albumin (Alb) concentration: The concentration of albumin was determined in plasma according to the assay described by (Cannon, *et al*, 1974).

Determination of Gamma-Glutamyl transferase: Gamma Glutamyl transferase was determined in plasma as described by (Saw *et al*, 1983).

Determination of Total protein: Total protein was analyzed in plasma as described by (Schultze and Heremans, 1966).

Determination of Total and direct Bilirubin: Total and direct bilirubin were analyzed in plasma by the method of (Tietz 1990).

Determination of catalase (CAT) activity: Catalase activity was estimated in plasma according to (Aebi 1984).

Determination of Superoxide dismutases (SODs): Superoxide dismutases (SODs) activity was estimated in plasma according to (Nishikimi *et al.*, 1972).

Results

HPLC of chicory

The flavonoids and phenolic acids are known to possess antioxidant activities due to the presence of hydroxyl groups in their structures and their contribution to defense system against the oxidative damage due to endogenous free radicals is extremely important. (Saggu, *et al.*, 2014). HPLC analysis of chicory for the phenolic compounds (table 1) showed the presence of 17 compounds which were varied in their amounts. It is observed that Catechin and Caffeic acid are found in high levels and their amounts were 2926.598 and 1268.448 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$ dry weight. While Protocatechuic 47.778 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$ dry weight and Apigenin-7-glucoside 27.697 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$ dry weight found

in moderate amounts. But, Chlorogenic acid 1.403 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$ dry weight and Lutiolin 0.605 $\mu\text{g}/100\text{g}$ dry weight found in low amounts in chicory. Chlorogenic acid, Caffeic acid and *p*-coumaric acid were 17.84, 35.22 and 9.655 % (Mona, *et al.*, 2009). Chicoric acid at a high percentage (64.70%), Isochlorogenic acid (8.90%), Dicafeoylquinic acid (6.87%), Chlorogenic acid (4.81%), Esculetin (3.54%), Caffeic acid (3.40%) (Kanj, *et al.*, 2019).

Liver function tests

Aspartate and Alanine transaminases of liver activity (AST) and (ALT): It was clear that, H_2O_2 treatment increased AST and ALT significantly from 23 and 25 at zero-time and reached 155 and 107 U/L after 45 days, respectively.

Data in table (2) showed that the most effect was observed by treatment with methanol chicory extract 75 mg/kg b.w which decreased AST and ALT parameters from 155 and 107 to 38 and 40 U/L after 45 days, respectively

Alkaline phosphatase and Plasma albumin Level (ALP) and (Alb): Table (3) show that the most effect was observed by treatment with methanol chicory extract 75 mg/kg b.w where ALP parameter decreased from 255 to 120 U/L after 45 days. Also, it is observed that the Alb parameter is significantly

decreased in positive control comparing with negative control. The most effect was observed by the treatment with methanol chicory extract 75 mg/kg bw which increased Alb parameter from 2.8 to 3.9 g/dl after 45 days.

Gamma GT and Total Protein (GGT) and (Tp): From table (4), it can be seen that GGT parameter decreased from 171 to 51 U/L after 45 days by treatment with methanol chicory extract 75 mg/kg bw. Total protein (Tp) parameter is significantly decreased in positive control comparing with negative control from 6.4 and which reached 4.85 g/dl after 45 days. The most effect was observed by treatment with methanol chicory extract 75 mg/kg b.w increased Tp parameter from 4.85 to 6.55 g/dl after 45 days.

Total and Direct Bilirubin: Table (5) shows that at zero-time H₂O₂ treatment increased total bilirubin significantly from 0.56 which reached 2.12 mg/dl after 45 days. Methanolic chicory extract 75 mg/kg bw decreased total

bilirubin from 2.12 to 0.75 mg/dl after 45 days. Also, it can be observed that the direct bilirubin is significantly increased in positive control 1.11 mg/dl comparing with negative control 0.11 after 45 days. The most effect was observed by the treatment with methanol chicory extract 75 mg/kg bw which decreased DB from 1.11 to 0.21 g/dl after 45 days.

Antioxidant activity

Catalase and Superoxide dismutase activity (CAT) and (SOD): Table (6) shows that the CAT and SOD parameter is significantly decreased in positive control from 3.11 and 47 U/mL respectively to 1.89 and 23 U/mL respectively comparing with negative control. The most effect was observed by the treatment with methanol chicory extract 75 mg/kg bw which increased CAT and SOD parameter from 1.89 and 23 U/mL respectively to 3.02 and 41 U/mL respectively after 45 days.

Table (1): HPLC analysis of phenolics and flavonoids of chicory

Compound	Chicory (µg /100g)
Gallic acid	21.407
Protocatechuic	47.778
<i>p</i> -hydroxybenzoic acid	7.462
Gentisic acid	18.890
Catechin	2926.598
Chlorogenic acid	1.403
Caffeic acid	1268.448
Syringic acid	2.062
Vanillic acid	17.228

Scopoletin	ND
Ferulic acid	90.918
Sinapic acid	9.857
<i>p</i> -coumaric acid	ND
Rutin	509.948
Naringinin	ND
Apigenin-7-glucoside	27.697
Rosmarinic acid	3.469
Cinnamic acid	2.205
Lutiolin	0.605
Apigenin	ND
Kaempferol	ND
Chrysin	10.559

Table (2) Effect of chicory extracts on liver function (AST) and (ALT) against H₂O₂ toxicity in rats

Name and unit	AST (U/L)				ALT (U/L)			
	zero	15	30	45	zero	15	30	45
Negative	23	23	23	24	25	25	25	25
Positive	23	84	110	155	25	82	98	107
chicory 50	23	82	63	40	25	81	69	47
chicory 75	23	80	61	38	25	80	61	40

Table (3) Effect of Chicory extracts on liver function (ALP) and (Alb) against H₂O₂ toxicity in rats

Name and unit	ALP (U/L)				Alb (g/dL)			
	zero	15	30	45	zero	15	30	45
Negative	92	92	92	92	4.1	4.1	4.1	4.1
Positive	92	168	212	255	4.1	3.62	2.6	2.12
chicory 50	92	143	136	126	4.1	3.41	3.75	3.84
chicory 75	92	140	135	120	4.1	3.4	3.81	3.92

Table (4) Effect of Chicory extracts on liver function (GGT) and (Tp) against H₂O₂ toxicity in rats

Name and unit	GGT (U/L)				T.p (g/dL)			
	zero	15	30	45	zero	15	30	45
Negative	24	24	24	24	6.4	6.4	6.4	6.41

Positive	24	82	157	171	6.4	6.11	5.8	4.85
chicory 50	24	81	65	57	6.4	6.11	6.34	6.43
chicory 75	24	81	59	51	6.4	6.01	6.39	6.55

Table (5) Effect of Chicory extracts on liver function (TB) and (DB) against H₂O₂ toxicity in rats

Name and unit	TB (mg/dL)				DB (mg/dL)			
	zero	15	30	45	zero	15	30	45
Days Treatment	zero	15	30	45	zero	15	30	45
Negative	0.56	0.56	0.56	0.56	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11
Positive	0.56	1.2	1.49	2.12	0.11	0.38	0.71	1.11
chicory 50	0.56	1.16	0.92	0.81	0.11	0.35	0.27	0.23
chicory 75	0.56	1.12	0.84	0.75	0.11	0.33	0.23	0.21

Table (6) Effect of Chicory extracts on antioxidant activity (CAT) and (SOD) against H₂O₂ toxicity in rats

Name and unit	CAT (U/mL)				SOD (U/mL)			
	zero	15	30	45	zero	15	30	45
Days Treatment	zero	15	30	45	zero	15	30	45
Negative	3.11	3.11	3.11	3.11	47	47	47	47
Positive	3.11	2.72	2.12	1.89	47	38	30	23
chicory 50	3.11	2.36	2.88	2.94	47	29	34	39
chicory 75	3.11	2.79	2.91	3.02	47	30	36	41

Discussion

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) is an important cause of oxidative injury because it can easily transform into a hydroxyl radical, which is one of the most destructive free radicals. Moreover, the half-life of H₂O₂ is comparatively longer than that of other reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Clarkson, and Thompson, 2000). H₂O₂ uses aquaporins to cross cell membranes rapidly (Henzler, and Steudle, 2000) and therefore, has the ability to diffuse in and out through

the cell membrane (Gemayel, and Klyubin, 1999). The hepato-protective effect of some plants was investigated in rats with oxidative stress induced by H₂O₂, which is a commonly used in animal model (Al-Malki and Abo-Golayel 2013). The liver is very susceptible to toxicity produced by reactive metabolites because it is a major site of xenobiotic metabolism (Liu, *et al.*, 2010). Free radicals are known to play a definite role in a wide variety of pathological manifestations. Antioxidants fight against free radicals and

protect us from a variety of diseases. Phenolics are known as non-enzymatic antioxidants and the antioxidant activity of phenols is mainly due to their redox properties, which allow them to act as reducing agents, hydrogen donors and singlet oxygen quenchers. (Sharma and Dietz, 2009; Thirugnanasampandan and Jayakumar, 2011). In the assessment of liver injury, the analysis of enzyme levels such as AST, ALT, and GGT is largely used and located in the cytosol of hepatocytes. Elevated levels of serum enzymes are indicative of cellular leakage and loss of functional integrity of cell membranes in the liver (Drotman and Lawhan, 1978). Increased serum ALP and bilirubin levels and decreased of Alb and Tp are related to the function of hepatic cells. Administration of H₂O₂ caused a significant elevation of enzyme levels such as AST, ALT, ALP and GGT, as well as total bilirubin, and decreasing of Alb, Tp, CAT and SOD when compared to negative control (Tables 2 to 6). (Huo, *et al.*, 2011 Zamani-Moghddam, *et al.*, 2012; Xie, *et al.*, 2012). The present study demonstrates that chicory methanolic extract attenuates liver damage due to H₂O₂ administration as indicated by the significant reduction in the elevated levels of ALT, AST, ALP, GGT, Total, and Direct bilirubin in

serum; increase in Tp, Alb, SOD and CAT in serum. These effects of methanolic extracts due to this plant contain antioxidants. Many biologically and chemically active substances have been investigated in chicory (Nwafor, *et al.*, 2017; Wang, *et al.*, 2017; Zlati'c and Stankovi, 2017; Thorat and Raut, 2018). The flavonoids and phenolic active compounds in this plant can act as hepato-protective agents because of their antioxidant and scavenging properties and protect rats against H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress in liver. This assumption was confirmed by the observed CAT and SOD in this study. Moreover, the maximum protective effect of methanolic extract was observed in H₂O₂-treated rats administered with 75 mg/ kg body weight. Apigenin induces cell cycle arrest at different proliferation stages (Kashyap, *et al.*, 2018). Also promotes different anti-inflammatory pathways (Huang, *et al.*, 2010). (McKay and Blumberg, 2002) who revealed that physiological responses to catechin may be relevant to the promotion of health, as well as the prevention or treatment of these chronic diseases. Chlorogenic acid and caffeic acid are antioxidants in vitro (Rice-Evans, 1996). Further, chlorogenic acid can inhibit DNA damage (Kasai, *et al.*, 2000). (Ou and Kwok, 2004) showed that ferulic acid

exhibits antioxidant activity in response to free radicals via donating one hydrogen atom from its phenolic hydroxyl group, as a result it shows strong anti-inflammatory activity. The resonance stabilization of ferulic acid is the main cause of its antioxidant nature. In addition, the reactive oxygen species of ferulic acid show the scavenging effect, which is similar to that of superoxide dismutase (Graf, 1992). (Barone, *et al.*, 2009) showed that free radical plays a major role in treatment of cancer, therefore antioxidants present in diet have fastidious consideration as potential inhibitors of abandoned cell growth. (Nemec, *et al.*, 2016) reported that gallic acid can exert its cytotoxic and antitumor effect via modulation of antioxidant/pro-oxidant balance. In some cases, the compound can control the reactive oxygen species (ROS)-induced carcinogenesis through increasing the activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), glutathione reductase (GR), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and/or by reducing the lipid peroxidation and ROS production. (Jagan, *et al.*, 2008) showed that in the case of hepatocellular carcinoma, gallic acid decreased the tumor size and the serum level of tumor marker enzymes such as aspartate transaminase (AST), alanine transaminase (ALT), lactate dehydrogenase

(LDH), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), and gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) by inhibiting the proliferation of hepatic cells. (Khan *et al.*, 2012a; Khan *et al.*, 2012b) evaluated the protective effect of rutin in carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄)-induced liver injuries in rats. Administration of rutin caused a decrement in levels of alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, alkaline phosphatase and gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase in serum raised due to carbon tetrachloride (Schwingel *et al.*, 2014).

Conclusion: Chicory is a medicinal plant used in traditional system of medicines. Finding of the present study indicates that the wild chicory could be a good source of natural antioxidants that might have a high possible significance as remedial agent in inhibiting or slowing down oxidative stress related diseases. Methanolic leaf extract of chicory exhibited highest activities suggesting methanol as an optimal solvent for phytochemical extraction. Powerful antioxidant ability of the plant extract for various in-vitro antioxidant assays may be attributed due to the occurrence of antioxidant compounds in this plant such as phenols, flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, etc. Thus, this study is step towards understanding the nature of the bioactive

compounds in this medicinal plant and further investigations will lead to actual liver disease treatment.

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